

EDUCATIONAL AND EDUCATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE APPLICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC LESSONS IN COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOLS

Omarkulova Shohida Nematillo qizi

Associate Professor of the Department of "Music Education" of the
Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15379815>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th May 2025

Accepted: 09th May 2025

Online: 10th May 2025

KEYWORDS

Secondary schools, music lessons, pedagogical technologies, creativity, education, music teacher, student.

ABSTRACT

Today, the use of modern methods and technologies in education is gaining importance. Especially in music lessons, the use of advanced pedagogical technologies can increase the interest of students, make them more active and creative. Music develops students' aesthetic taste, imagination, hearing and creative abilities. Therefore, special attention should be paid to increasing the activity of students in these lessons. In this sense, this article broadly covers the theoretical and practical foundations of the use of pedagogical technologies in music lessons in secondary schools.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022, No. PF-134 on approval of the National Program for the Development of School Education for 2022-2026, developed specific guidelines for the formation of knowledge and skills of schoolchildren, their upbringing in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, increasing the prestige of the teaching profession and the quality of teachers, improving textbooks and educational methodological complexes in accordance with the requirements of the time, creating modern models of school educational institutions that meet international standards, and developing social and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies.

With the help of pedagogical technologies, lessons can be made more interesting, interactive and effective. This forms in students such skills as independent thinking, a creative approach to music and the promotion of new ideas. Each student has a desire to express himself, learn new things and create. If lessons are organized properly, this desire will be easier to fulfill.

Here we will define the words technology and creativity. The concept of "technology" entered science in the 70s of the last century in connection with technical progress and is formed from two Greek words technos - art, craft and logos - science, doctrine, and means the science of craft. [6,15-b].

Educational or teaching technology is a system for achieving, applying, and managing the effectiveness of the entire process of teaching and learning, taking into account human and technical resources and their interaction, in order to optimize educational models. [6].

In general, educational technology is a set of methods and tools used by a teacher to effectively organize lessons and teach students knowledge, skills and competencies. In other words, it is a way to plan, explain, practice and check the results of a lesson in an easy and understandable way.

“Creativity” is derived from the English word “create” and means to create. Creativity is thinking out of the box, coming up with new ideas. Creativity means abandoning tradition and going beyond conventional thinking.

In sources, creativity is described as a personal quality (virtue) of a person that manifests itself in the process of forming a person or a personal characteristic of a person, which is associated with his self-improvement and development.

Based on the above, we can say that pedagogical technologies are a set of various methods and techniques aimed at effectively organizing the teaching process and facilitating the process of students' learning. In the modern education system, the correct selection and use of pedagogical technologies increases students' interest in the lesson, encourages independent and creative thinking. In this process, students independently master the lesson under the guidance of a teacher, creatively approach the knowledge they have learned and search for it.

It is worth noting that ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education and upbringing is an important role in ensuring the correct, meaningful, and interesting organization of the educational process aimed at students' mastering the lesson, in this process, students become active participants in the lesson, independent and creative thinkers, active individuals who can freely express their opinions and defend their opinions.

Studying, observing and analyzing practical experiences in the application of pedagogical technologies in education shows that organizing classes based on interactive methods is becoming widespread in almost all areas of education. In our opinion, this should not lead to the conclusion that one or another type of pedagogical technology should be used in every lesson. When will advanced pedagogical technology be effective, when it is interesting for students, can activate them, direct them to independent and creative thinking, observation.

For this, when choosing pedagogical technology, the teacher should use it taking into account the topic, structure of the lesson, the interests of students, and, if it is music lessons, their theoretical, practical, and performance capabilities.

The main goals and objectives of the use of pedagogical technologies include: Organization, cooperation (teacher-student interaction), group and individual work, ensuring the activity of each student, improvement, analysis, comparison, generalization, drawing conclusions, control, evaluation, etc.

In the process of teaching subjects, it is advisable for each teacher to work according to the following preparation system for the use of pedagogical technologies:

- Identifying the topic;
- Correctly setting and defining the goal;
- Determining the keywords that need to be mastered on the topic;
- Determining tasks 1,2,3,4....;
- Drawing up a scenario of the technological process;
- Individual work;
- Group (small group) and team work;
- Kahoot, question-and-answer, discussion, cluster, brainstorming, etc. with the whole team.
- Regulations;

- Evaluation;
- Conclusion;

Ready-made technologies are first applied to the educational process, those that have been experimentally tested and have yielded positive (high) results.

- Here, we would like to dwell on the notable features of the application of advanced pedagogical technologies to educational conditions:

- In studying any subject, students are not only taught, they are taught to study and learn independently;

- The knowledge and concepts given to students are not given ready-made, but students are taught to independently collect and study information and data on the subject using sources;

- Skills are developed in working with the curriculum, textbooks, and texts;

- The student is accustomed to expressing, defending, and proving his/her opinion;

Currently, in the entire education system of our republic, in the secondary education system, great importance is attached to improving the quality and efficiency of teacher training, and various pedagogical research is being conducted in this regard. Most of this research is aimed at increasing the efficiency of education by introducing advanced pedagogical technologies into education in order to achieve the goal of education and its high results, and the technologization of education is one of the most important tasks.

In connection with the organization of innovative activities on a scientific basis, the most important thing in introducing advanced pedagogical technologies into the educational process is to take into account the readiness and interests of students for this activity and to select the necessary technology.

“Technologizing the teaching process in music education means implementing the teaching process using multimedia tools, various software capabilities, and musical sound editing equipment.” [2-Gozal Davronova “Innovative Technologies in Music Teaching” textbook Samarkand-2024 (p. 15)] For example, using computers and multimedia tools in the teaching process - showing video lessons in music lessons, listening to the sounds of musical instruments, performing exercises through interactive programs.

Lessons enriched with slides, graphics, audio and video materials make it easier for students to understand the topic and increase their interest in the lesson. In general, technologization is the modernization of lessons, increasing the student’s enthusiasm for learning, and using methods to effectively convey knowledge.

As we can see, the use of pedagogical technologies in music education is one of the important directions of the modern educational process.

With the help of pedagogical technologies in music lessons:

- increase students' interest in music,
- develop their creative thinking,
- form the ability to learn independently and be creative,
- create the opportunity to conduct lessons in a lively and interesting way.

Thus, through pedagogical technologies, it is possible not only to impart knowledge, but also to develop the creative activity of students. Therefore, increasing the creative activity of

students by organizing music lessons on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies remains an urgent issue.

To develop creative activity, it is necessary to create opportunities for students to conduct independent research and experiments with music. For example, students can be given the task of selecting and analyzing their favorite musical works or performing them in a new style. This process forms in students the habit of working on themselves, researching and creating. They can discover their talents through independent musical exploration.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2022 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" No. PQ-112
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 15, 2024 "On measures to radically improve the teaching of musical culture in secondary schools and develop the professional activities of teachers of this subject" No. PQ-391
3. G. M. Sharipova Z. Khodjaeva. Music teaching methodology (textbook) Tashkent, "NIF MSH" 2020.
4. G.M. Davronova "Music Teaching Methodology" textbook Samarqand 2021
5. G.M. Davronova "Innovative Technologies in Music Teaching" textbook Samarkand-2024.
6. Hamdamova M. Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of the Mechanism for Developing the Intellectual Potential of Youth. Methodological Recommendations. – Tashkent, 2007. pp. 10-25.